

Evaluation of the Job Satisfaction of the Nursing Staff of the National Hospital of Donka: Case of the Trainee Doctors

TOURE H [1], DIEDIOU B [2], TOURE CA [1], BAH .H[1]

1 University of Conakry

2 University of Dakar

Corresponding author : Habib TOURE: Occupational physician, assistant head of clinic, Faculty of Medicine, Conakry
President of the Guinean Society of Occupational Health and Safety Professionals (SOGUIPROSST)

Abstract:-

➤ Introduction

Job satisfaction is still an unknown concept in Guinea. Our study aimed to assess job satisfaction among trainee doctors at Donka National HI.

➤ Material and Methods

This was a cross-sectional descriptive study which was conducted within the Donka National Hospital, for a period of 6 months from June 14 to December 14, 2021. Were included in our study, any trainee doctor in service at the Donka National Hospital and agreeing to participate and answer the study questionnaire. The study variables were quantitative and qualitative.

➤ Results

During this study, we interviewed 350 trainee doctors, 306 of whom agreed to answer our questionnaire, a rate of 87.4%. The average age of our respondents was 29.3 ± 2.7 years. There was a male predominance of 67.6% with a sex ratio (M / F) equal to 2.1. Singles were the dominant marital status at 69.2%. The average seniority of our respondents was 2 ± 1.5 years. The average level of satisfaction was 49.9%, which corresponds to the level of the Likert scale to the “dissatisfied” modality. Dissatisfaction at work was noted for the dimensions “working conditions”, “stability of your job”, “application of company procedures” and “remuneration”.

➤ Conclusion

Our study shows an unsatisfactory level of work among trainee doctors at the Donka National Hospital. The main sources of dissatisfaction were pay and working conditions. Improving the working and living conditions of trainee doctors would be of great importance for their better job satisfaction.

Keywords:- Satisfaction, Work, Trainee Doctors, Donka National Hospital.

List of abbreviations

CAMES: African and Malagasy Council for Higher Education

CHU: Centre Hospitalier Universitaire

HND: Hôpital National Donka

IT: Job dissatisfaction

MSQ: Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire

OT: Work Organization

IR: Interpersonal Relations

SP : Patient Care

ST : Job Satisfaction

TCEM: Third Cycle of Medical Studies

AFNOR : Association Française de Normalisation

I. INTRODUCTION

Job satisfaction (JS) is defined as a pleasant or positive emotional state resulting from a person's evaluation of his or her work or work experiences [2].

For Adams and Bond, job satisfaction would represent the degree of positive affect towards a job or its components [3].

Among health care workers, job satisfaction is perceived as their opinion of their professional achievements at work in terms of the quality of care they provide, the time they have available for their care activities and the pleasure they derive from it [4].

Physicians' satisfaction can be affected by personal and contextual factors, as well as by the intrinsic characteristics of the medical profession. The assessment of job satisfaction among caregivers is based on the analysis of three main factors:

- Interpersonal relations (IR) {relationships between colleagues, interaction and communication, teamwork, peer support, social climate and ethics...} ;
- Work organisation (WO) {workload, work environment, pay and benefits, work diversity, autonomy, support from hierarchy, work-family relationship, personal and professional development};

- Patient care (PC) {relationships with patients, opportunity for high quality care, meaning of patient care...}[5-8].

The PRESST-NEXT study conducted in 2008 among health care workers in 10 European countries showed a job dissatisfaction (JI) rate of 77.9% in Italy, 64% in Germany, 69.5% in France [9].

In China, Xiao C et al in 2020 reported over 75% of the effect of job satisfaction on hospital performance [10].

In Africa, studies are rare, a study conducted in Dakar by. Diatta A.E.R et al. in 2017 among interns in Dakar hospitals revealed that 73.6% were satisfied, 9.4% very satisfied and 17% neither satisfied nor dissatisfied. The average level of job satisfaction was 68.07% [11].

It is in this context that we initiated this study whose general objective was to evaluate job satisfaction among trainee doctors at the Donka National Hospital in the Republic of Guinea in order to propose effective prevention strategies applicable to this very sensitive sector of social life

II. METHODS

➤ Study Setting

The Donka National Hospital served as the setting for our study. It is one of the reference centres of last resort in the health pyramid and together with the Ignace Deen National Hospital, forms a university hospital centre (CHU) in Conakry. It is composed of 26 departments (Emergency, Haematology, Infectious Diseases, Cardiology, Psychiatry, Nephrology, Paediatrics, Diabetology-Endocrinology, Internal Medicine, Dermatology-Venerology, Anaesthesia-Resuscitation, Anatomopathology, Maxillofacial Surgery, Odontology-stomatology, Visceral surgery, Obstetrics and gynaecology, Trauma and orthopaedic surgery, ENT, Thoracic surgery, Oncological surgery, Paediatric surgery, Plastic surgery, Neurosurgery, Medical imaging, Laboratory, Pharmacy).

The material consisted of trainee doctors from Donka National Hospital of Conakry

A mixed questionnaire was used as a support, including

- Socio-demographics data;

- Data from the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ). [9] (See questionnaire in appendix).

➤ Methods

Type and period of study

This was a cross-sectional, descriptive study conducted at the Donka national hospital in Conakry, for a period of 6 months from 2 August 2021 to 1 February 2022.

• III-4- Selection criteria

- **III-4-1- Inclusion criteria** are all trainee doctors on duty at the DNH of Conakry who agreed to participate in the study.
- **III-4-2- Criteria for non-inclusion:** all doctors at Donka University Hospital and administrative staff as well as those who did not agree to participate in the study.

The study variables were qualitative and quantitative, including socio-demographic data Age: Sex Nationality Seniority Speciality

➤ Marital Status

MSQ data:

- Evaluating all aspects of the job according to two groups of factors:
- The group of extrinsic factors, known as "atmosphere factors": working conditions, relations between colleagues, hierarchical supervision, recognition;
- And the group of intrinsic factors known as motivators: the use of abilities, the diversity of tasks, autonomy, innovation, the feeling of accomplishment. [9]
- Evaluating the level of satisfaction thanks to the Likert-type scale of which there are five modalities:
- -Between 20% and 50% corresponds to "dissatisfied";
- -Less than 20% corresponds to "very dissatisfied" [11].
- -Data analysis

Data entry and analysis were done in Epi info version 7. Tables and figures were made to see the distribution of the phenomenon. Statistical tests were used to compare frequencies and means.

III. RESULTS

This was a cross-sectional, descriptive study conducted at the Donka National Hospital
The response rate was 87.4%.

Fig 1: Distribution of trainee doctors by participation rate.

Table I: Distribution of trainee doctors by age group.

Age group (years)	Number	Percentage
≤ 25	7	2,3
26 – 30	228	74,5
31 – 35	65	21,2
36 – 40	6	2
Total	306	100
Average age 29.3 ± 2.7 years		Extremes: 25 years and 40 years

Table II: Distribution of trainee doctors by specialty

Specialty	Number	Percentage
Haematology	36	11,8
Nephrology	21	6,9
Resuscitation	21	6,9
Thoracic surgery	19	6,2
Oncology	19	6,2
Traumatology	19	6,2
ENT	18	5,9
Internal medicine	16	5,2
Cardiology	15	4,9
Dermatology	15	4,9
Infectious disease	15	4,9
Gynaecology	13	4,2
Neurosurgery	13	4,2
Pediatric surgery	11	3,6
Ophthalmology	11	3,6
Pediatrics	11	3,6
Maxillofacial surgery	9	2,9
Emergencies	7	2,3
Visceral surgery	6	2
Orthopaedics	6	2
Anapath	5	1,6
Total	306	100

Table III: Distribution of trainee doctors according to MSQ data

MSQ data	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neither satisfied Neither satisfied	Satisfied	Very satisfied
1) Your opportunities for advancement	27 (8,8%)	68 (22,2%)	34 (11,1%)	146 (47,7%)	31 (10,1%)
2) Working conditions	77 (25,2%)	133 (43,5%)	25 (8,2%)	67 (21,9%)	4 (1,3%)
3) Opportunities to do different things from time to time	9 (2,9%)	52 (17%)	64 (20,9%)	168 (54,9%)	13 (4,2%)
4) Your importance to others	1 (0,3%)	35 (11,4%)	55 (18%)	169 (55,2%)	46 (15%)
5) The way your supervisor manages his or her employees (human relations)	10 (3,3%)	48 (15,7%)	38 (12,4%)	157 (51,3%)	53 (17,3%)
6) Your manager's competence in decision making (technical skills)	7 (2,3%)	33 (10,8%)	32 (10,5%)	161 (52,6%)	73 (23,9%)
7) The opportunities to do things that are not contrary to your conscience	6 (2%)	36 (11,8%)	83 (27,1%)	160 (52,3%)	21 (6,9%)
8) The stability of your job	49 (16%)	113 (37%)	60 (19,6%)	77 (25,2%)	7 (2,3%)
9) Opportunities to help people in the company	14 (4,6%)	54 (17,6%)	63 (20,6%)	150 (49%)	25 (8,2%)
10) Opportunities to tell people what to do	7 (2,3%)	59 (19,3%)	63 (20,6%)	150 (49%)	27 (8,8%)
11) Opportunities to do things that use your abilities	8 (2,6%)	33 (10,8%)	53 (17,3%)	186 (60,8%)	26 (8,5%)
12) The way in which the company's internal rules and procedures are implemented	39 (12,7%)	91 (29,7%)	80 (26,1%)	84 (27,5%)	12 (3,9%)

Table IV: Distribution of trainee doctors according to MSQ data (continued).

MSQ data	Very dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neither satisfied Neither satisfied	Satisfied	Very satisfied
13) Your salary in relation to the importance of the work you do	144 (47,1%)	79 (25,8%)	50 (16,3%)	31 (10,1%)	2 (0,7%)
14) Opportunities to make decisions on your own initiative	25 (8,2%)	72 (23,5%)	79 (25,8%)	121 (39,5%)	9 (2,9%)
15) Opportunities to stay busy all the time during the working day	13 (4,2%)	65 (21,2%)	42 (13,7%)	177 (57,8%)	9 (2,9%)
16) Opportunities to try your own methods of doing the work	16 (5,2%)	86 (28,1%)	86 (28,1%)	111 (36,3%)	7 (2,3%)
17) Opportunities to work alone in your job	15 (4,9%)	70 (22,9%)	126 (41,2%)	83 (27,1%)	12 (3,9%)
18) How well your colleagues get on with each other	4 (1,3%)	44 (14,4%)	69 (22,5%)	153 (50%)	36 (11,8%)
19) The compliments you receive for doing a good job	15 (4,9%)	46 (15%)	49 (16%)	148 (48,4%)	48 (15,7%)
20) The sense of accomplishment you get from your work	10 (3,3%)	38 (12,4%)	35 (11,4%)	141 (46,1%)	82 (26,8%)
Average	8,1%	20,5%	19,4%	43,1%	8,9%
Average level of satisfaction: 49.9%		Modality: "Dissatisfied"			

IV. DISCUSSION

This was a cross-sectional, descriptive study conducted at the Donka National Hospital

- The response rate was 87.4%.
- Semachew A. et al. in 2017 in Ethiopia [29] reported a response rate of 92.7%.
- Diatta A.E.R. et al. in 2019 in Senegal [11] reported a participation rate of 72%.
- This massive participation could be justified by the availability of trainee doctors to participate in the study in order to improve their living and working conditions.
- The most represented age group was between [26 - 30] years, i.e. a frequency of 74.5%, the average age of our respondents was 29.3 ± 2.7 years with extremes of 25 and 40 years.
- Owona Manga L. J et al. in 2018 in Cameroon [30] found an average age of 39.19 ± 8.9 years and the most represented age group was between 30 and 39 years, i.e. 57.3%.
- This result could be explained by the fact that the majority of the respondents were young subjects, who are much more numerous in the departments as trainee doctors.
- The assessment of job satisfaction among the trainee doctors showed that on average 43.1% were satisfied; 20.5% dissatisfied; 19.4% neither satisfied nor dissatisfied; 8.9% very satisfied and 8.1% very dissatisfied. The average level of overall satisfaction was 49.9%, which corresponds to the "dissatisfied" Likert scale.

Of the twenty aspects of work evaluated by the MSQ, four dimensions were identified as sources of dissatisfaction among the trainee doctors, namely

- Remuneration with 47.1% very dissatisfied, 25.8% dissatisfied and 16.3% neither satisfied nor dissatisfied;
- Working conditions with 43.5% dissatisfied and 25.2% very dissatisfied;
- The stability of your job with 37% dissatisfied and 19.6% neither satisfied nor dissatisfied;
- The application of procedures with 29.7% dissatisfied and 26.1% neither satisfied nor dissatisfied.

Concerning the dimension of possibilities to work alone in your job 41.2% were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied.

On the dimension of the methods to do the job, 50% for the way your colleagues get along with each other, 48.4% for the compliments you receive for doing a good job and 46.1% for the sense of accomplishment you get from your job.

Estryn-Behar M. in 2008 reported in France and in Europe a rate of dissatisfaction at work of 77.9% in Italy, 64% in Germany and 69.5% in France with the main reason among French carers being the lack of psychological support in the face of the emotional burden, the lack of a job and the lack of a job description [10]. Aspects related to working conditions and the working environment dominate these

sources of job dissatisfaction among European healthcare workers.

Diatta A.E.R. et al. in 2019 in Senegal [11] reported that the respondents were globally satisfied with their work, i.e. 83%, and the average global job satisfaction score was 68.07. On the other hand, the reasons for dissatisfaction with the job found among the respondents were working conditions, remuneration and the application of procedures.

Opoku S et al found the same findings in Ghana in 2014 with a moderate overall satisfaction of doctors and a dissatisfaction with their work linked to the non-adapted use of their capacities, remuneration and the difficult balance between professional and private life.

These results could be explained by the poor working and living conditions of the trainee doctors, which demonstrated their dissatisfaction with their work, and thus impacted on their medical performance.

V. CONCLUSION

Job satisfaction is still a poorly understood concept in Guinea. Our study of trainee doctors at the Donka National Hospital revealed that young, mostly single, subjects were the most represented, with a male predominance. The average global satisfaction score was 49.9%, corresponding to the "dissatisfied" modality on the Likert scale. The main sources of job dissatisfaction remain working conditions, job stability, the application of internal company procedures and remuneration.

The improvement of working and living conditions and the promotion of participatory management are urgent measures to be adopted in order to ensure the well-being and a better level of job satisfaction of trainee doctors at the Donka National Hospital.

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